

(1917 words)

Eichmann on the Playground

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When I was in the fourth grade, arriving at school early meant we could buy penny candy from the man in the red shack next to our derelict brick building. For a nickel he would sell us pastel colored sugar dots on long strips of white paper, licorice shoe laces, red or black, and small paper packets of Lickemade that stained our palms vivid red, orange, or green. Then we would take turns seeing who could balance the longest on a capped pipe that rose two feet above the asphalt playground. Girls wore dresses to school then, and leather soled shoes and ankle socks. It was there, standing on my right foot, arms spread wide, left foot held to one side to keep me steady, but not too high so the rough boys from Keansburg and Port Monmouth couldn't look up my skirt, that I first heard details of the Nazi atrocities. It was Spring, 1961; I was nine.

They leaned in close, these boys who came to school bruised and sometimes bloody and who would tie other boys to the fence and beat them till their eyes swelled shut and their noses began to bleed. Once one of them came to school with a long nail driven through his finger, fooling us all till he tore the bandage off, laughing as he showed us the fake blood and the rusty metal that curved to fit over the tip of his finger. Another sat in front of me so that I could see the livid orange mercurachrome on a patch of shaved scalp with real stitches closing a real wound inflicted by his father, who had struck him with a pitchfork. My own father, a career Army officer who had served in New Guinea and the Philippines in 1944 and 45 and then in occupied Germany in 1946, suffered fits of

terrifying and inexplicable rage. He had carried back with him, and brought into our house, to our family table, things he had witnessed and been compelled to do, of which he never spoke, but which tormented him and terrified us. Though we hardly knew the extent of it, we lived, all of us, in the shadow of World War II, barely sixteen years behind us.

I remember standing there on the pipe, my longest time aloft ever, cool air all around me, so that I could trace the outline of my undershirt and pants, the collar, cuffs, and hem of my dress as the fabric was moved by April wind around my strong little body, and the bad boys leaned so close that I could see the chapped skin of their unwashed cheeks and look down on the spikes of their uncombed hair.

“Did you hear what the Nazis did to the Jews?” one said, his voice hoarse with excitement as all the children with both feet on the ground drew closer. “They turned them into soap and made lampshades out of their skin.”

“Yeah,” said the other, “and they hung their babies from meat hooks.”

Before I could stop them, images formed in my mind. I envisioned strangely colored bars of soap lined up on a bare wooden table, like the brown lump my mother used on us when we broke out in a rash from poison ivy; I could see soft light glowing through the taut pale skin of a lampshade like the one on my parents’ night table. I felt myself disappear then, flow right out through my eyes, up past the fat buds on the trees, out over the chain link fence that ran the length of the blank schoolyard.

The Eichmann trial had begun. A man whose name immediately became a household word, Adolph Eichmann had been kidnapped in May of 1960 after stopping to buy cigarettes on his way to a mindless factory job he held under an assumed identity in

Argentina. The former SS officer who organized the Final Solution, overseeing the destruction of six million European Jews, tracked by Israeli undercover agents since 1945, had been spirited back to Israel in extreme secrecy, where he was now, almost a year after his abduction, standing trial.

On Easter Monday, April 3, 1961, in preparation for the trial that would begin in Jerusalem a week later, the *New York Herald Tribune*, which I devoured every morning before going to school, carried a photograph of Dachau in 1945 on its front page. A skeletal man covers his genitals with a prison camp shirt while his emaciated bunkmates look back at the photographer holding the camera. “*The living dead we found in the Nazi camps when Hitler’s Germany fell,*” the caption reads. But that is not how they looked to me. The man hiding his nakedness had intelligent eyes. He looked knowing and sad. They were individuals, these men, frightening to me not because they were dead, but because they were alive, and each in his distinct posture looked as if he might open his mouth and speak at any moment. A little further below the photograph, the newspaper announced the first in a series reporter Robert S. Bird would write on the death camps now, “Return to the Scene in ’61: The Most Monstrous Crime,” and then prepared us for his coverage of the trial to come, “So Men Won’t Forget.” But how could the danger be forgetting when we were about to hear for the first time what had actually happened from people just like these silent, staring men?

The world now felt split in two, the past overcoming the present by its vast scale and the horror that now confronted us all. Which world was I supposed to dwell in—this dark world of extreme brutality and suffering—or the sunlit one shown in a photo on the same front page, with lovely Jackie Kennedy, elegant in a blue shantung suit and

matching pillbox hat standing in the doorway of a Catholic church in Palm Springs, Florida after Easter Mass, our handsome, smiling president, not yet 45, following behind her? No one seemed able to offer us a way to bridge these worlds, to tell us how they might be connected.

A week later, as the trial got under way—briefly overshadowed by the sensational news that the Russians had put a man in space and returned him safely to earth—a half page ad ran in the *New York Times*. “The judgment of Eichmann,” small white letters on a large black ground announced. “We are, we have reason to think, creatures of reason,” the text below the big black box began. “Yet the evidence, in numbers and in pictures, of this man’s crimes defies all reason, rejects all belief...How, then, do you judge a man accused of murdering millions?”

But that was not the question the soap and lampshades made of human beings woke in me.

The professional ad man’s high moral tone then gave way to the real message, as reporters from all over the world competed for a share of the audience for the first televised criminal trial in history: *The Eichmann Trial...starting 6:30 PM tonight (and continuing every weeknight, Monday through Friday)...WABC-TV, Channel 7.*

At home, after supper and homework, we could watch the Mickey Mouse Club, with the latest installment of the continuing adventures of Spin and Marty on the dude ranch, and watch as Tinker Bell sent a shower of little stars over the castle of Disneyland with the touch of her magic wand—or the Eichmann trial. On the playground, kids struggled to master double Dutch jump rope and exchanged bits and pieces of lurid gossip about what “the butcher” had done to “the Jews”—always they were an undistinguished

mass, fearful in their suffering, and so, reduced to anonymity despite their portraits, with tattooed numbers on their arms, in LIFE magazine. Back in our classrooms, we had to be taught the names and faces of our presidents, but we had no trouble recognizing Eichmann's twitching face and long thin body, photographed through the glass walls of his prison cell, as he was served matzos during Passover by Israeli guards who were forbidden to speak with him, or as he lay reading on his cot, or turned to face the wall, a dark mound under blankets, his slippers neatly lined up on the floor as he slept, one bare bulb illuminating his cell. Our teachers continued to hand out three-lined paper and fat brown pencils, training our small hands to form the long loops of a capital G or S in cursive, and said nothing about what we were all seeing and reading and hearing in magazines, newspapers, and on TV. Day after day for sixteen weeks, as Eichmann sat within a glass, bullet-proof cage in the courtroom, people "who had climbed naked out of mass graves, or had miraculously escaped from gas chambers or had managed to throw themselves from death trains" took the witness stand and testified.* And all around us as the age of testimony was being born, adults maintained a painful silence. No one knew what to say.

The trial "that laid before the world for the first time minute details of the attempted extermination of the Jews" ended on December 11th, 1961, just days after my tenth birthday, when Eichmann was found guilty on all fifteen counts against him. On December 15th, as we prepared for Christmas, the *Tribune* announced the sentence of the court: "Eichmann Will Hang." The long process of adjudicating his appeal and rejecting his pleas for clemency on the grounds that he was only following orders would not end

until the last day of May 1962, when Eichmann was escorted to the gallows as spring, in all its beauty, bloomed.

For that long year, as details of Nazi atrocities streamed into our daily lives through the portals of the mass media, with little sense of how to integrate the truth that was emerging, I was haunted by involuntary thoughts and images composed from fragments of survivors' stories. I was unable to stop myself from seeing a living room furnished entirely with human bodies, naked people on all fours used by the clothed and indifferent as chairs and tables, hat racks, ashtrays, and mirrors. I felt I was supposed to choose which side to be on, and I couldn't, because each was so terrible. Waking or sleeping, I soon found myself numbered among the naked and defenseless. Then I could no longer be a little girl in a cotton dress who could lean down and buckle her shoes with confidence. I experienced this as my personal failure, and told no one.

It was in the intimate act of reading memoirs and novels by survivors that the frightening spectral figures of the Jewish victims left behind by the Eichmann trial were finally replaced by living beings, men and women and children, each with a story. The warm, human voice whose mysterious presence on the page summoned me, inviting me to remain present, offered me the unexpected gift of release from fear and shame and guilt that I had not known what to do with the public spectacle of the trial. What I could not bear as a child I learned to bear as an adult, as literature—the record of our humanity—offered me, the reader, no less than the writers, an extended moment in which they could speak and I could listen as the ancient act of storytelling bridged the gulf between us.

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